

**Bridging the security, privacy, and data protection gap for
smaller enterprises in Europe**

D7.1 The SENTINEL website and visual identity

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
D7.1	Deliverable 7.1
MEs	Medium Enterprises
SMEs	Small-Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.1 “The SENTINEL website and visual identity” is produced within Work Package 7 (Ecosystem building, Exploitation and sustainability management) of the SENTINEL Project, under Task 7.2, Dissemination and communication strategy to trigger awareness and new business opportunities.

This document gives a general review of the SENTINEL website which is available at www.sentinel-project.eu and provides the necessary functions and information to act as a dissemination strategy tool and information recourse of the project. The website will be used by the consortium as well as external stakeholders, to disseminate the project’s activities, outputs, findings and the whole research progress of the project.

The main content, functions and the usability of the website will continue to be managed, improved and edited during the project lifetime. Thus, certain menus and images shown in this deliverable are going to change.

1. Introduction

Over 25 million European SMEs/MEs, central within EU enterprise policy, face multiple challenges related to personal data protection; ranging from awareness to a clear and practical roadmap to compliance, the most prominent one is the fact that, unlike larger enterprises, SMEs/MEs lack access to enterprise-grade cybersecurity technology and capacity-building for compliance, making them increasingly often victims of costly data breaches. SENTINEL aspires to bridge this gap by boosting SMEs/MEs capabilities in this domain through innovation at a cost-effective level. SENTINEL will integrate tried and tested modular cybersecurity technologies with fresh, ambitious ones, such as a novel Identity Management System for human-centric data portability towards enabling a unified “European Data Space”, and an end-to-end digital personal data protection compliance self-assessment framework for SMEs, into a unified digital architecture. Data from these modules will then undergo disruptive Intelligence for Compliance through SENTINEL’s digital core, featuring machine learning-powered recommendations, policy drafting & enforcement for compliance and a ‘one-stop-shop’ incident response center.

Combined with a well-researched methodology for application, an open knowledge sharing hub and a wide-reaching plan for experimentation, SENTINEL will catalyse adoption of market-leading security tech among SMEs/MEs and help safeguard their and their customers’ assets.

1.1 Purpose of the Document

This document presents the website of the SENTINEL project as a dissemination and communication strategy tool for worldwide audience, comprising a comprehensive provision of information, as well as a shared platform for the project team. The SENTINEL website address and links to social media pages will be included in all dissemination materials of the project (fliers, leaflets, posters, newsletters and other promotional material).

Work Package 7 of SENTINEL (Ecosystem building, Exploitation and sustainability management) focuses on ensuring that the various outcomes of the project are widely disseminated to the appropriate target group, at the appropriate time and via appropriate methods. Furthermore, WP7 aims at identifying stakeholders who can contribute to the development, evaluation and uptake of the project outcomes and encouraged them to participate in the project’s current and future actions.

The main objectives of WP7 are:

- Develop the project’s visual identity;
- Raise awareness about the project concept, developments and findings to all key actors;
- Develop the dissemination and communication strategy of the project;
- Develop the SENTINEL business model and strategies for incentivizing/promoting project adoption;
- Create a marketing strategy that focuses on commercialization.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The document is structured in a way similar to how a visitor would navigate in the project's webpages; it presents the components of the SENTINEL website with images as screenshots of the pages, starting from the website home page, the "About" tab and all relevant sub-tabs (Concept, Innovation, Work plan, Use cases), the Consortium tab, the Knowledge Hub tab and its subcomponents (Deliverables, Publications, Dissemination material) and finally the News & Events tab.

1.3 Intended readership

This document is intended for both consortium members and external to the project stakeholders, since it comprises a rich information content platform about the project's main principles, components, participants, latest news and upcoming actions.

2. Website Home Page

The “Home” page of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>) serves the following functions:

- It provides access to the other sections of the website (main menu);
- It presents a short overview of the SENTINEL project, the main scope and objectives;
- It provides a short description of each Work Package;
- It presents a short description of the SENTINEL’s Use Cases;
- It presents the project consortium including partner’s logos and respective links;
- It informs about the latest news and events;
- It provides links to SENTINEL’s social media accounts.

Figure 1 presents a sitemap of SENTINEL’s website, showing the site’s structure, the hierarchy of the different pages on the site and how these are interlinked. Information on the site is organized in a way to facilitate ease navigation for both users and crawlers.

Figure 1. Sitemap showing structure of SENTINEL’s website.

The SENTINEL Home page is presented in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. SENTINEL Home page.

The website has been designed to adapt its contents according to the platform that access it (desktop, tablet, smartphone). Figure 3 presents a screenshot of the website homepage, when accessed through a smartphone.

Figure 3. SENTINEL home page screenshots when accessed through a smartphone.

3. Website About Tab

The “About” tab of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>) presents four components (Figure 4):

1. The Driver - The *Driver* section stresses the motivation behind the project, which is driven by regulatory and data protection laws.
2. The Constraint - The *Constraint* section focuses on the limitations that SMEs/MEs face nowadays in adopting efficient enterprise-grade security and personal data protection mechanisms.
3. The Opportunity – The *Opportunity* section highlights the rising prospects with regard to SMEs/MEs shifting from conventional cybersecurity solutions to more intelligent, cloud-based cybersecurity solutions.
4. The Challenges – The *Challenges* section mentions current barriers with regard to IT infrastructure complexity that currently comprises a major challenge for SMEs/MEs towards evolving their data protection mechanisms and practices.

Mandate to follow regulatory and data protection laws

In the last decade SMEs have been massively hit by sophisticated cyber-attacks, leading to substantial financial losses. According to Accenture, 43% percent of cyberattacks are aimed at small businesses, but only 14% are prepared to defend themselves, leading to losses of \$200,000 on average. Organizations are continuously looking for advanced security solutions to combat such disruptive attacks; they are required to meet mandatory security standards, failing which they must pay hefty fines to governments. Data and privacy breaches cause massive data loss to organizations and hamper their brand image. The various regulatory standards include many more than the EU's GDPR. For example, the Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard (PCI DSS), HIPAA, FISMA, Federal Trade Commission (FTC), Gramm-Leach-Bliley Act (GLBA), EU Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA), and the Homeland Security Act, to name just a few.

Figure 4. SENTINEL About page.

3.1 Website Concept Tab

The “Concept” page of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>) under the “About” tab, presents the overall concept of the SENTINEL project by clarifying its main propositions and depicting a detailed architecture diagram with SENTINEL’s components and offerings (Figure 5).

Figure 5. SENTINEL Concept page.

3.2 Website Innovation Tab

The “Innovation” page of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>) under the “About” tab, provides the four main innovation paragraphs describing the project’s innovation scope accordingly in each different service (Figure 6):

- INNOVATION 1: The SENTINEL identity management for data portability
- INNOVATION 2: A complete GDPR compliance framework
- INNOVATION 3: Real-Time Cyber range training and assessment services
- INNOVATION 4: Leveraging the score method to identify challenges, needs and compliance processes in SMEs/MES

Figure 6. SENTINEL Innovation page.

3.3 Website Work Plan Tab

The “Workplan” page of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>) under the “About” tab, displays the work plan of the project and contains an image showing how the 9 WPs interlink with each other (Figure 7).

By clicking in each WP, the objectives, deliverables, lead beneficiary of the Work Package and duration, are presented.

THE INNOVATION PROGRAMME OF SENTINEL IS ORGANISED INTO 9 INTERLINKED WORK PACKAGES (WPS).

Work Packages

- 1. SENTINEL BASELINE: SETTING THE METHODOLOGICAL SCENE
- 2. THE SENTINEL PRIVACY AND PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION TECHNOLOGIES
- 3. THE SENTINEL DIGITAL CORE
- 4. THE SENTINEL SERVICES
- 5. SENTINEL CONTINUOUS INTEGRATION AND SYSTEM VALIDATION
- 6. REAL-LIFE EXPERIMENT EVALUATIONS: SENTINEL PILOTS
- 7. ECOSYSTEM BUILDING, EXPLOITATION, AND SUSTAINABILITY MANAGEMENT
- 8. PROJECT MANAGEMENT, COORDINATION AND QUALITY ASSURANCE
- 9. ETHICS REQUIREMENTS

Figure 7. SENTINEL Work Plan page.

3.4 Website Use Cases Tab

The “Use Cases” tab of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>) under the “About” tab, provides the three Use Cases of SENTINEL (Figure 8). A brief description of each use case appears in each of the three blocks (please, note that the third use case consists of multiple application use cases, and thus cannot be described in the block).

The three Use Cases of the SENTINEL project:

- ClinGenics A micro-enterprise
- Tristone Investment Group – An SME
- SMEs/MEs engaged via Digital Innovation Hubs – UNINOVA

Figure 8. SENTINEL Use Cases page.

By clicking on each Use Case, a detailed description is presented, including short profile information of the pilot enabling partner, current challenges they face, as well as the envisioned set of services to implement through SENTINEL. Figure 9 shows an example of the ClinGenics use case study.

Figure 9. Detailed use case study (example for ClinGenics use case).

4. Website Consortium Page

The “Consortium” tab of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>) presents all 14 project partners, starting with the coordinator (Figure 10). By clicking on each row, a brief description of the identity of each partner is shown together with their role in the SENTINEL project (Figure 11). It also shows the partner’s logo and a tab “Website”, which redirects the user to the partner’s official website, where further information about the company can be found.

Figure 10. SENTINEL Consortium page.

Figure 11. Partner's profile information, role in the project and website link (example for ITML).

5. Website Knowledge Hub Tab

The “Knowledge” tab of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>) offers a drop-down list with three sections.

- Deliverables
- Publications
- Dissemination Material

5.1 Deliverables

The “Deliverables” page of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>), under the “Knowledge Hub”, presents a table with a list of SENTINEL deliverables (Figure 12). The full text of public deliverables will become available as the project progresses.

Figure 12. SENTINEL Deliverables page.

5.2 Publications

The “Publications” page of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>), under the “Knowledge Hub”, will provide an update of the project’s publications (journal papers, workshop papers), showcasing the dissemination progress of the project (Figure 13).

Figure 13. SENTINEL Publications page.

5.3 Dissemination Material

The “Dissemination Material” page of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>), under the “Knowledge Hub”, will provide up-to-date supporting material (press releases, brochures, newsletters, videos, flyers, posters, etc) during the project lifetime (Figure 14).

Figure 14. SENTINEL Dissemination page.

6. Website News & Events Tab

The “News & Events” tab of the SENTINEL website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>) provides information in relation to various project events and meetings. Latest tweets feeds are extracted from SENTINEL’s official Tweeter account and are presented on the right side. The following figure displays a recent post referring to the project’s Kick-off meeting (24/25 June 2021).

Figure 15. SENTINEL News & Events page.

Conclusion

The SENTINEL website has been created by ITML, responsible for deliverable D7.1, as part of Task 7.2 “Dissemination and communication strategy to trigger awareness and new business opportunities”. The website will be continuously managed by ITML throughout the project duration and will be maintained three years beyond the end of the project. The project website will act as a project management tool and an information repository, and together with the social media channels (LinkedIn and Tweeter) will serve as a dissemination tool during and beyond the end of the project.